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Accreditation of Flemish Civil Engineers programmes (2016): an experience of cross-border Quality Assurance

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ABSTRACT

In the Yerevan Communiqué (2015) ministers in charge of higher education in the EHEA promoted the transnational aspects of quality assurance (QA). However, the internationalisation of the QA activities is far from having reached the objectives assigned by the ministers. The main hindrance comes from the national regulations, which do not allow or strongly restrain home institutions to call for accreditation by foreign agencies.

Although experiences of transnational accreditations of programmes are not unusual, and calls to international experts in national accreditation teams tends to be a standard, the delegation to a foreign agency of the quality assessment of the whole national engineering education, is a rather unique experience.

This paper deals with the accreditation of all the Flemish civil engineer's programmes in Belgium by the French agency CTI. It describes shortly the origin and the building of the project, and gives the analyses of the experience from the respective point of views of the accreditors (CTI) and of a senior representative from an accredited institution (KU Leuven).

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INTRODUCTION

From the origin of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), the Conferences of ministers in charge of Higher Education, emphasize the international dimension of QA (Quality Assurance); in the Bucharest communiqué [1], they set as a priority to “allow (..) registered quality assurance agencies to perform their activities across EHEA, while complying with national requirements”.

Despite the noted advances of the Bologna process, the internationalisation of the QA activities is far from having reached the objectives assigned by the ministers. The main hindrance comes from the national regulations, which -apart in some countries as for example Germany or Switzerland- do not allow or strongly restrain home institutions to call for accreditation by foreign agencies. To this must be added the language barrier and the widespread feeling that the foreign experts team may not perceive and understand the national specificities.

If experiences of transnational accreditations are reported, very few deal with a complete field of higher education. This paper deals with the accreditation of all the Flemish civil engineering programmes in Belgium by the French CTI agency, which is a rather unique experience as quality assessment of a whole national field of education, delegated to a foreign agency. It will be described in the following sections; respectively, the origin and the building of the project (sect. 1); the analysis of the experience from the accreditors (CTI) point of view (sect. 2), and the view from a senior representative of an accredited institution (KU Leuven) (sect. 3).

1 THE ORIGIN AND THE BUILDING OF THE PROJECT

1.1 The “Commission des Titres d’ingénieur” (CTI)

In France, the “Commission des titres d’ingénieur” (CTI) is an accreditation body established 80 years ago (1934) by the French law, responsible for setting the standards for the “titre d’ingénieur diplômé” (master degree of engineering science) and for the programme accreditation in higher education institutions willing to deliver it. CTI is an autonomous institution equally composed on the one hand of representatives of employers and professional engineers, and on the other hand of academia [2]. CTI contributed to the Bologna process in the French engineering domain; it is member of ENQA (European Network for Quality Assurance), registered in EQAR (European Quality Assurance Register) and a founding member of ENAEE (European Network for Accreditation of the Engineering Education).

In addition to its national QA activities (more than 200 Higher Education Institutions delivering engineering degrees to about 35 000 graduates per year), CTI has set standards and procedures for transnational accreditation [3] and has a well-established international experience (about 130 programmes accredited in Belgium, Bulgaria, Burkina Faso, China, Switzerland, Viet Nam; others in process in Tunisia, Morocco, etc.). Transnational accreditation is part of CTI’s mission from its beginning; its founding law states that the graduates of foreign accredited programmes are entitled

to hold the "titre d'ingénieur diplômé" and have the same professional recognition in France as graduates of national institutions (procedure of "Admission par l'Etat"). CTI is authorized by ENAEE [4] to award the EUR-ACE® label to the programmes which fulfil the Framework Standards and Guidelines (EAFSG) [5].

1.2 The three Flemish Universities and the national context

The three Flemish civil engineer's programmes involved in the procedure described in this paper are organized by the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (Brussels), KU Leuven University (Leuven) and Ghent University (Ghent).

Since the 1990's, visitations (and later accreditations) of higher education institutions are mandatory in Flanders. This is organized, together with The Netherlands by the NVAO (Nederlands-Vlaamse Acreditatie Organisatie). Visitations were planned by programme, and took place every 8 years. Nearly every year some programmes were visited. For the universities, this was a large burden. A long, separate Self Evaluation Report had to be written for every visitation. The commissions that came for the visitations, often had several non-engineer members, giving sometimes rise to comments that were not perceived by the faculties and their teaching staff as to the point, but rather out of scope.

Replacing this system by a visitation by CTI was a great opportunity for several reasons. First, it is an accreditation by engineers. The supposition was that the comments would be more tailored towards the engineering field. Second, CTI looks at the 5-year programme (3 years of Bachelor, and 2 years of Master) as a whole. As the specific competences that are crucial for an engineer are introduced in the Bachelor, and further developed in the Master programmes, only accrediting the Bachelor, or only accrediting the Master, makes less sense. Third, the CTI approach visits the whole faculty in one movement. This allowed all programmes of each faculty to join forces in quality assurance. It was an opportunity to sharpen their vision and objectives, and to write texts at the level of the Faculty, which was not done before in a systematic way. Last but not least, the texts required by CTI were perceived as much more to the point than the texts that used to be asked by the NVAO. They were less extensive, much more focused. A 50-page Self Evaluation Report had to be written for the faculty and each programme had to write a specific report of 4 pages. This allowed the faculty to concentrate on the essentials.

1.3 The project building

The first contacts with CTI were informally taken in 2010 and then at the SEFI conference in Leuven in 2013. Under the aegis of the Flemish Interuniversity Council (VLIR), CTI and the Flemish faculties set a procedure, based on agreed Terms of Reference (TOR, January 2014).

Before the starting of the accreditation procedures, a change occurred in the legal context. On June 2015, the Flemish Parliament approved a revision to the system of quality assurance and accreditation in higher education, with an evolution towards full institutional accreditation in 2020 and a suspension of the previous programme accreditation system. Consequently, NVAO and VLIR were released from their commitments in the agreed process.

However, even though they were no longer legally required to do so, the three faculties decided to go on and to ask CTI alone the accreditation of their engineering programmes. A latest version of the Terms of Reference (TOR September 2015) was worked out, where the three faculties "seek accreditation by CTI through the procedure of "admission par l'Etat" with the possibility to "request the EUR-ACE label".

The degree programmes concerned by the assessment process comprise:

- Bachelor programmes (180 ECTS): Bachelor of Engineering and Bachelor of Engineering Architecture. These programmes have no professional objectives, almost all their graduates immediately enter a master degree programme in line with the options they selected during their Bachelor studies; as such these programmes are neither eligible for the procedure of “admission par l’Etat”, nor for the EUR-ACE label; however, their quality was assessed and a review report published with recommendations.
- Master programmes (120 ECTS): most of these programmes are taught in English; to be compliant with the Flemish regulation they are also offered in Dutch; as the two tracks share the same learning outcomes, they were considered as a single degree programme. When Master degree programmes were jointly prepared by two (Flemish) universities, one faculty was selected to present the application on behalf of the two. Some Masters programmes presented by Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) are joint programmes with the French-speaking “Université Libre de Bruxelles” (BRUFACE project). All these Master programmes are eligible for “Admission par l’Etat” and for the EUR-ACE label.

At least, the Flemish faculties were successful in their application to the European project Erasmus; consequently, several master programmes asking for accreditation are prepared by a consortium of European universities; they were presented by the Flemish university of the consortium, although it was not always clear that all the members were equally informed of the accreditation process and that they equally share the same learning objectives.

2 THE ACCREDITOR’S VIEW

Beyond the needs of human resources and the organisation constraints, the accreditation campaign was a very rich and demanding experience for CTI and for the persons who contributed to it.

The objective of this section is not to present a comprehensive report on the accreditation results (which are available on the CTI website [6]), but to present the insights which can be extracted from such an experience and to contribute to the enhancement of international collaborations in Quality Assurance [7].

2.1 The favourable key factors

The accreditation campaign was not the result from a top-down decision of the University directions or from legal requirements, but from a collective initiative of the deans and of the programme managers. This has resulted in a remarkable implication of all faculty staffs, an outstanding quality of the self-evaluation reports and a very active participation to all the audit meetings. The operations -notwithstanding their complexity- were made easier too by the culture of Quality Assurance obviously implemented in the faculties and shared by the academic and administrative staff, which does not imply a total agreement on the objectives of the process (see below).

The three universities involved have clearly their own personality owing to their history and cultural backgrounds; however, the engineering studies are regulated at the national level by stringent regulations – sometimes considered by the experts as too stringent-; this homogeneity saved experts’ time and efforts, as they could rapidly focus on each faculty specificities.

2.2 Specific issues

CTI national language is French, Dutch is the national language of the Flanders; it was decided that the working language would be English and that the main documents, including the self-evaluation report (SER), must be written in English. Most masters

are taught in English and the Flemish students and teachers speak fluent English; however, a very sizeable amount of student works and of teaching documents were written in Dutch; the participation of Dutch speaking experts was very helpful although the scientific contents of the documents allowed the experts to grab their topic and level. Besides the need to translate from Dutch to English some key documents and to translate to French the experts' report for the CTI plenary session, the language issues have not raised important difficulties.

The three universities are research-driven and roughly built on the so-called "von Humboldt" model with a strong emphasis on the scientific excellence and on the academic freedom of professors in their research and lectures [8]; this feature clearly favours the individual initiatives and the bottom-up approach to the collective decisions; it may however contradict with the Quality Assurance culture in general which assigns collective objectives and collective assessment methods.

At several occasions, such ongoing misalignments showed up in the interviews or in the documents when individuals or teams seemed reluctant to apply the policy globally approved at the faculty or at the university levels.

In Flanders, the employment of the civil engineers is very good, with a high demand for graduates. The employers report their difficulties to hire skilled employees in this domain. Clearly the less than 1 000 civil engineers graduating per year in Flanders are far from fulfilling the national (and international) job market needs, taking also into account that many engage in Doctorate studies. This excellent employment situation does not induce the engineering faculties to develop the employability of their graduates; the experts regretted the lack of statistics on the engineers' job market, the average time for job search for each programme, the professional trajectories of the graduates, etc., that one expects from pre-professional curricula.

2.3 The case of the "international" curricula

A difficulty arose for the "international" curricula and especially the Erasmus Mundus programmes (or their successors when the Erasmus contract is ended). They are high level and highly selective programmes, the scientific quality of which is not arguable. However, engineering programmes -particularly according to the CTI and ENAEE's criteria- are pre-professional degrees, the accreditation of which must guarantee that every graduate acquired the skills and competences expected from an engineer and specified in the outcome profile published by the faculty.

In the pool of universities which support the transnational degree, it was sometimes difficult to assess that all partners are aware of and that all implement at the same level the pedagogical objectives and methods, which are subject to assessment in the visited university (here Flemish). There were sometimes evidences of the contrary: the curriculum which is designed in Flanders as an engineer degree with all its all-about, is presented as a pure research degree in a partner university. Furthermore, owing to the Erasmus rules, students may obtain the degree from a university where they spent a small part (if not no part at all) of their studies; if this is not arguable from a purely academic point of view, it raises very important issues for the entry into the profession and for the relation with the employers.

3 THE VIEW OF THE LEUVEN FACULTY

KU Leuven is a comprehensive university, with over 55.000 students. It is a typical research-oriented university, member of LERU (League of European Research Universities). It is well ranked internationally, especially for innovation.

The Faculty of Engineering Science (FES) counts over 3.500 students. It offers 2 Bachelor's programmes (a general Bachelor of Engineering, and a Bachelor of

Engineering: Architecture), 12 Master programmes and 6 advanced Master programmes. In the departments over the FES, more than 1.000 PhD students are doing research. The largest part of research funding is acquired through competitive calls.

3.1 Approach taken

Quality assurance is the task of all people involved in education. The FES has a small support team that gives assistance for quality assurance where needed in the Faculty. This team was strengthened by one extra person for 2.5 years.

First, for each of the Bachelor's and Master's programmes, a detailed set of learning outcomes was identified and formulated in the ACQA framework (Academic Competences and Quality Assurance [9]). This was followed by a comprehensive curriculum mapping, linking courses to outcomes. This effort has led to valuable insights into the structure, strengths and weaknesses of each programme.

Second, all course descriptions (so called ECTS files in Leuven) were revisited. Special attention was given to the correct formulation of the goals of each course, and of a detailed description of evaluation criteria and organization.

Third, several questionnaires were launched. One aiming students finishing their degree. The questions pertained the whole of the curriculum, and covered all classical areas of quality assurance. The answers complemented the regular questionnaires organized by the university for each course at least every 3 years. A different questionnaire was sent to the alumni of the faculty, focusing on the more recent alumni of the last 5 years.

Fourth, several industrial advisory boards (IAB) were installed as not every programme had the tradition of meeting regularly with representatives of industry.

The curriculum mappings, the output of the questionnaires, and the comments of the IABs, were used to discuss in length, both at the level of the faculty as at the level of each individual programme, an extensive SWOT analysis. These SWOT analyses resulted in actions plans, again both at the level of the faculty as at the level of each programme.

The writing of the faculty SER was started about 18 months before the deadline. The good table of contents of CTI allowed the FES to describe its vision, strategy and processes in a structured and comprehensive manner. The SER was complemented with several annexes, giving more details about topics such as programme outcomes and the extensive problem solving and design pathway. The SER of the faculty was extensively discussed at all levels of the faculty (including the students) and with the Senate (specifically the vision and strategy aspects).

3.2 Research-oriented nature of the KU Leuven

The fact that the KU Leuven is a typical research-oriented university has its influence on several aspects. First, the education is given by top researchers in their field. The students are involved in the research (through several projects and their master thesis), and special attention is given to research skills. As professors are keen on hiring top PhD students, they pay a lot of attention to education. Furthermore, often the top researchers are also the best lecturers! Researchers have an innovation mindset, and are ready to innovate in their education – as long as the university and faculty do not ask to change everything every 6 months!

However, education is not always the main focus of top researchers. They often are more concerned with their own contributions to the programme (contributions that are focused on their research), than with the programme as a whole. This led CTI to qualify the programs as content-driven, and less as output-driven.

3.3 Outcome of CTI for KU Leuven

The exercise of self-evaluation, and all the activities described above to prepare the visitation by CTI boosted the quality assurance mind set, and gave rise to a global enthusiasm towards quality of education, and this both at the faculty level as at the level of each individual programme. The texts that were produced were written in a way that they could be re-used on websites, in brochures, in university-wide actions. The visitation itself, and the report by CTI, although interesting, brought less new insights. At the level of the faculty there was a short but sharp analysis. The strong points included the first rated scientific environment, the research-driven focus and the high level of acquired scientific competences by the students, initiatives such as ACQA [9] and the programme solving pathway, and the quality of the provided documents. Some of the weak points are a result of the research-driven focus, such as lacking a comprehensive view and proper management of non-scientific learning outcomes, and the reluctance to some extent of involving all external stakeholders in the formal supervision of programme content and outcomes.

The level of feedback for each individual programme varied strongly. The feedback was never extensive.

It is clear that the main benefit of the whole process lies in the strong groundwork that was done. The preparation and the writing of the SER gave the faculty and its programmes a mirror. The process of CTI, including the table of contents of the SER, guided this reflection. For the faculty, this was a strong momentum.

3.4 The future

The legal landscape in Flanders has changed. In the meantime, visitations and accreditations of individual programmes have been put on hold by the Flemish government. A system of institutional reviews has been set up, where each institution for higher education in Flanders is visited as a whole, including its quality assurance system.

The new quality assurance system of the KU Leuven, called COBRA, is based on regular reflection meetings of primary actors (students, lecturers, other education staff). The problems that come up in these reflection meetings are either solved locally or are pushed to a higher level (first faculty level, than university level). Each 4 years external peers, the working environment and alumni are involved in the reflection.

The FES, as a faculty of the KU Leuven, will implement the COBRA system. The question is if they will continue the accreditation process with CTI. Having to conform to two separate systems of quality assurance is of course extra work. The EUR-ACE label that can be acquired through CTI is certainly an incentive for continuing with CTI.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper addresses most questions raised in the report on “cross-border quality assurance” [7] published by EQAR and the E4 group. It draws up the benefits and problems for both the agency and the institution points of view.

The main difficulty concerned the “international” curricula (i.e. supported by a pool of international universities); they enter in the category of “joint degrees” which are strongly promoted within the EHEA. Specific guiding principles [7] were not anticipated and then not met during the process, e.g. a) “the external quality assurance procedure should be based on a SER jointly submitted by the cooperating institutions, or b) the site visit should therefore include discussions with representatives of all cooperating institutions. For these programmes, notwithstanding their scientific excellence, the assessment could not be conclusive.

There is a strong ongoing debate on the pros and cons of programme accreditation vs. institutional accreditation; the programme accreditation performed by CTI in Flanders comprises an important institutional component, since all the degrees of each faculty were concerned in a single round.

Such a procedure is more efficient and allows to involve all the faculty staff for a self-assessment. However, as one can only expect to have one or two experts per domain, each professor has less chance to discuss in detail his/her teachings with a peer colleague; some may feel some frustration when they are eager to demonstrate the high scientific level of their teachings.

But the assessment could focus more on the general objectives and outcomes, and on the quality of pedagogical processes; more time was dedicated to the interviews of the governing bodies of the faculties and to the stakeholders (as the employers and alumni). A whole faculty assessment is then more coherent with the quality assurance fundamentals which aim to assess the quality of the internal processes and not to certify the detailed contents of the curricula [10].

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